

Understanding the ethical and privacy challenges in XR development for Off-Highway Industrial Machinery

Challenges and solutions:

Within the framework of the project, the University of Luxembourg was committed to better understanding the challenges faced by different stakeholders in the Off-Highway Machinery domain while participating in the design of the solutions. While there is a vast amount of discussion of XR impact on different domains, like education or entertainment, the discussion about industrial application of XR has only just started; therefore, it was important to create a roadmap for its design. The main challenge was to be able to gather a 360-degree perspective on the privacy and ethical issues (from the industry, developers and end-users "on the ground"); to do it, we needed to create a step-by-step approach, focus groups and guided discussions. It was difficult to find the right language and the right

approach to translate our concepts from HCI and design to the practical and goal-oriented view of our developers and end-users.

Impact:

We designed and iteratively redesigned and evaluated the Design Guidelines for Privacy and Ethics for Off-Highway machinery. During the extensive discussions with the members of the related EU projects and other EU and World-based stakeholders we shaped our vision of the Guidelines and demonstrated them to the relevant communities (we are now finalizing the Project-end version of Guidelines). In the future we are continue to work with the different initiatives (e.g., XRSI and Metaverse Standard Forums) to be able put our ideas into XR for ethics and privacy standards.

Figure 1: Guidelines evaluation during a workshop

KEY BENEFITS

Battery of methods for explication users concerns on XR in industrial settings

Integration in international networks of privacy and ethical XR

